

Some notes on shadows

Ryan J. Buchanan

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§0 Preamble

Conventions

By an isomorphism we will always mean a bijective n-categorical isomorphism. By a pushout or pullback, we will mean an n-pushout or n-pullback. We avoid working with the finer details of n-categories, but appreciate their relationship to one-categories for the purposes of localization.

Let $K = \partial K^2$ be a boundary-forming and simply connected space. Let the convex portion of space about K have an inner product

$$\mathbf{Sets} \times \mathbf{Top} \rightarrow \mathbf{DispMfld}$$

↓

$$\mathbf{SSets}$$

so that there is a projection onto a curve within $\mathcal{A}(K)$.

We will call K an (ϵ, δ) -chain, and we will call its pushout into $\mathbf{SSets}$ a “shadow.” We will operate using the commutative fusion rule

$$\epsilon \star \delta = \delta \star \epsilon = \mathbf{Hom}(\mathbf{Sets} \times \mathbf{Top}, -)$$

We characterize each unique geometric fibration $\theta \rightarrow \{-\}$ according to a “length spectrum,” which “records” information about the number of objects with maps into identical tangent categories.

Definition 0.0.1 A δ -transitive connection is a first-degree connection on an (ϵ, δ) -chain.¹

Let A be a geometric series with a least element α . Then, there is a relationship

$$\mathbf{sup}(A)\mathbf{R}\alpha$$

of rank p , which accords with the p -weight² of an associated module in A .

§1 Chain Transitivity

A sequence Q of weakly chained ind-spaces give a precise Fourier projection onto the interior of a topological space as determined by the display maps which foliate Q . We define Q to be a chain-connected space; that is, for any two elements $\{p, q\}$ in Q , they may be compared by $p\mathbf{R}q = (q\mathbf{R}p)^{\top}$.

¹ See [ChainTr]; we must cherish the authors of this paper for their marvelous account of the succession function, which had yet to make its more operadic appearance. [GSP] gives a similar indispensable account.

² See [Calc], pg. 13

We say a chain-connected space has the property of *chain transitivity* if, for any two sections

$$\{p_i \rightarrow q_i, p_i \rightarrow p_i\} \simeq \text{fib}(Q),$$

there are the retracts

$$\{q_i \rightarrow p_i, p_i \rightarrow p_i\} \simeq \text{cofib}(Q^{\text{op}})$$

This definition has been precipitated slightly beforehand, but now receives its precise incarnation.

Definition 1.0.1. A *display map*

$$\Phi_i : ((p \star q) \vee (q \star p)) \rightarrow ((p \vee q) \vee (q \vee p))$$

is a fusion-distributive logical connective.

Example

Let $\Phi_i(\mathcal{P}) \rightarrow \Phi_i^{-1}$ be a “twist” on an algebra $\mathcal{A}$. We call this map of displays $\Phi_i(-) \rightarrow \Phi_i(-)$ a *display block* if it covers a frame $\mathcal{I}$ in the π_0 -cocycle of an arbitrary system of involutions.

Here, an involution means a coefficient q attached to a function field f

$$\pi_0: q(f) \rightarrow ((q^{-1}(f)) \vee (q(f^{-1})))$$

Following [Beardsley], we will write $\mathbf{L}_n$ for the appropriate localization functor $\pi_0 \zeta \rightarrow \zeta$, where

$$\zeta = q(f) \rightarrow (-)$$

Let $\mathfrak{g}$ be an arbitrary geodesic in some presentable category. Then, we have a restriction from the *higher bundle* of $\mathfrak{g}$ to the $\mathfrak{g}$ -action *on objects*. This is a localization from the ∞ -Cats form of a representation to the geometric form.

Definition 1.1.0 A **Jordan form** is the kernel of some ζ -object. An object with a Jordan form satisfies the idempotent criterium on pg. 4 of [Jord].

Definition 1.1.1 Let $S: X \rightarrow X$ be a continuous map. A sequence $\{x_n\}$ in X is an asymptotic pseudo-orbit of S if³

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} d(S(x_n), x_n + 1) = 0$$

Remark It would be interesting, at least to the author, if every ζ -object object had an asymptotic pseudo-orbit.

For two rank one isomorphisms $x\mathbf{R}y$ and $x'\mathbf{R}y'$, we take the difference

$$\{x \cup y\} \setminus \{x' \cup y'\} = \omega$$

³ [Strong], definition 2.3

to be a pseudo-orbit of an $\mathbf{R}$ -algebra $\mathcal{A}$. If we let $\{x \approx x'\}, \{y \approx y'\}$ be distinct equivalence classes, then we can take the immersion

$$\gamma\omega \hookrightarrow \omega$$

from the outer sum of a pair and the inner hom of the other.

§2 Shadows

Definition 2.0.1 A *po-category* is a category $\mathfrak{PO}$ with a 2-isomorphism into the bi-category⁴ $\mathbf{SSets} \times \mathbb{I}$.

Definition 2.0.2 A *shadow category* is a po-category

$$\mathfrak{shad} = \text{Push}(\mathfrak{PO})$$

which is locally a pushout.

A shadow is a compactly generated object in $\mathfrak{shad}$, which is globally presentable.

Proposition 2.1.0 $\mathfrak{shad}$ is Cartesian-closed.

Proof Let ω_1, ω_2 be two real cones, with the inclusions

$$\omega_1 \in \mathfrak{PO}$$

$$\omega_2 \in \text{Push}(\mathfrak{PO})$$

The bijection

$$\omega_1 \leftrightarrow \omega_2$$

automatically makes $\mathfrak{shad}$ symmetric monoidal, which means it is Cartesian closed.

Let $\mathbf{L}$ be a diagram with a unique factorization $f: y' \rightarrow y$, where $\text{proj}\{y, y'\} = z$. Assuming each object is a po-category, we have an isomorphism

$$\mathfrak{shad} \simeq z$$

Definition 2.1.1 An *E-chain* is a strictly modellable set of integrands with morphisms into $\mathfrak{shad}$.

Here, we have explicitly defined the boundary-forming parts of an orbifold to be those series of fibrations which admit connections into the shadow category.

Proposition Any map $E \rightarrow \mathfrak{shad}$ is at least a $\underline{d}$ -shadowing.⁵

A “shadow” is, in some sense, any continued fraction which has stable approximation as an algebraic symbol σ .

$$\text{Map}(E, \mathfrak{shad}) \simeq \partial\sigma_k \rightarrow \sigma$$

Here, the left adjoint is a totally disconnected free variable.

We can compute this more simply by putting

⁴ Where $\mathbb{I}$ is the category of intervals

⁵ See [ChainTr], pg. 3.

$$\sigma_{\text{DISC}} \rightarrow \sigma_{\text{FIN}} = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} (d(\partial i, i)) = \pi_0(\tau).$$

Axiom 2.1.2 *Adjointness*

For two stable objects $\pi_0(\tau_0) \dashv \vdash \pi_0(\tau_{k+1})$, with adjoint morphisms f and f' , these morphisms shall be called *mutually orthogonal* and *metric-forming*.

We take a simple comparison triangle, $\tilde{\Delta} = \triangle abc = \sum_{\angle a}^c p^\circ$, and calculate, say, the standard deviation of each angle from the arithmetic mean. Then we obtain a measure of the hyperbolicity (as measured by the $\text{Cat}(k)$ -number) of a space, specifically a positive or negative sectional curvature.

References

- [Beardsley] J. Beardsley *Some notes on the category of p -local harmonic spectra* (2013)
- [ChainTr] W.R. Brian, J. Meddaugh, B.E. Raines *Chain transitivity and variations of the shadowing property*
- [GSP] A. Barzanouni, E. Shah *Chain Transitivity for maps on G -spaces* (2019)
- [Strong] M. Hirsch, H. Smith *Chain Transitivity, Attractivity, and Strong Repellers for Dynamical Systems* (2001) (Journal of Dynamics and Differential Equations)